

Formative Assessment in Mathematics: Students at the Centre of Learning

Thérèse Dooley

Emeritus Associate Professor, School of STEM, Innovation and Global Studies, Institute of Education, DCU

In this paper the findings of a recent systematic review on formative assessment (Shiel & Dooley, 2022) that pertain to the teaching and learning of mathematics are outlined. Reference is made to the meaning of formative assessment, its effect on learning, the nature and source of feedback, learning trajectories, and revelatory tasks. It is argued that effective formative assessment encompasses more than a set of tools – it is dependent on a learning environment that is characterised by student autonomy in learning and assessment.

Keywords: formative assessment, feedback, self-assessment, learning trajectories, revelatory tasks

Introduction

A question that arises for teachers in Ireland (and elsewhere) is how formative assessment can be used effectively in their teaching of mathematics, particularly as it is an integral aspect of the Irish primary and post-primary mathematics curricula. While a thorough and detailed consideration of this question is outside the scope of this paper, a recent review conducted by Shiel and Dooley (2022) yields some pertinent findings. The purpose of the review was to examine how formative assessment might support the development of literacy and numeracy.¹ However, as no reviews of formative assessment in numeracy were found, the scope of the search was broadened to include the term “mathematics”. An overview of relevant findings is provided below.²

Effect of Formative Assessment on Mathematics Learning

Despite over two decades of research on formative assessment there is no clear consensus on what it means. In 2009, Black and William proposed that assessment is formative “to the extent that evidence about student achievement is elicited, interpreted, and used by teachers, learners, or their peers, to make decisions about the next steps in instruction that are likely to be better, or better founded, than the decisions they would have taken in the absence of the evidence that was elicited” (p. 9). Adapted from their original interpretation (Black & Wiliam, 1998), it is broad in scope. It includes, for example, different agents of assessment (teacher, self or peer), evidence of learning, decision making and next steps. Researchers in the field identify different aspects of formative assessment as appropriate for their context – some focus on formative assessment as a set of tools to be used to improve teaching (e.g., scoring rubrics, checklists, mastery tests), others consider it as part of the

¹ The review was a component of a review of research in relation to literacy (including digital literacy) and numeracy commissioned by the Department of Education in Ireland (Kennedy et al., 2023).

² A bibliography of research cited in this paper can be found in Shiel and Dooley (2022).

teaching and learning process (e.g., effective use of teacher questioning, provision of feedback that supports students in setting new learning goals) and still others conceptualise it as neither one nor the other but some integration of the two.

Initial reviews showed the effect of formative assessment on achievement to be very promising; however, more modest, mixed effects are revealed in recent research. This is true for mathematics as well as for other subject areas. There are many reasons for this including the nature of the reviews, how achievement is defined and how formative assessment is conceptualised in specific research. Given the complexity of formative assessment, the focus of different reviews tends to be on features of formative assessment interventions. Findings are often ambiguous. Formative assessment with technology, for example, is found to have no more impact on achievement than formative assessment without technology. However, there is some evidence that online assessment is most effective when based on mathematics content that is aligned to a clearly defined hierarchy of skills. It is also concluded that, in such instances, feedback provided to students should be immediate and frequent. Other research points to the need for feedback to be provided to students within and between instructional units rather than within and between lessons (medium-term versus short-term). Much depends on the nature of the task being assessed. There is an indication in some studies that immediate feedback is more effective for lower-order learning than delayed feedback and vice versa. Coupled with this, and probably not of great surprise, is that feedback incorporating an explanation and focusing on strategies that helps students to bridge the gap between where they are and where they want to be is particularly beneficial for higher-order outcomes.

Learning trajectories focus on students' successively more complex way of thinking about a topic. Although nomenclature varies, they are increasingly a feature of curricula, e.g., they are included in the new Primary Mathematics Curriculum in Ireland³ as "progression continua". Due to their relative novelty, research on effect of learning trajectories is limited. However, there is some evidence that they can benefit formative assessment by the teacher if they are used in combination with a range of other teaching strategies such as encouraging children to share ideas, take risks and learn from and with peers in mathematics lessons. Moreover, student-facing checklists⁴ based on trajectories can support younger students to self-assess and set goals.

Key to effective formative assessment are revelatory tasks that provide teachers or learners or peers with a "window into students' thinking" (William, 2007, p.1069) so that decisions can be made about appropriate next steps. Interviews with students, observation of them engaging in cognitively challenging tasks, documentation of their talk and investigations of samples of work are some of the fruitful ways that formative assessment information can be gathered. In particular, student-generated diagrams, concepts maps and writing about learning show some promise as formative assessment tools in mathematics.

³ The new Primary Mathematics Curriculum had not been published at the time of writing this paper; hence the information reported derived from a draft version of this curriculum (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment, 2022).

⁴ Such checklists have been paraphrased so that they can be understood by students.

In the main, outcomes of reviews are nuanced – some researchers attribute this to the implementation of only certain principles of formative assessment, without consideration of the broader implications for classroom practice. However, self-assessment is highlighted as having a significant impact on achievement. It is a process whereby students reflect on the quality of their work, make decisions about the degree to which it meets particular goals and revise as appropriate (Andrade & Valtcheva, 2009). Many believe its powerful effect to be related to the role it plays in students’ metacognition and self-regulated learning, both of which are significant factors in improving academic attainment (Muijs & Bokhove, 2020). Also emerging from the literature is the positive effect of peer-assessment on students’ subsequent performance. Further studies are required to elucidate beneficial types of peer assessment (e.g., use of rubrics, written or dialogue component). However, there is little evidence that the provision of grades by peers – particularly in primary and post-primary schools – enhances learning. A significant finding about self- and peer-assessment is that they have much greater effect than either teacher-directed assessment or no assessment. While it remains difficult to pinpoint effective features of self- and peer-assessment, the overriding conclusion reached by many is that the most important factor underpinning effective formative assessment is a classroom environment where the student is at the centre of learning.

Final Remarks

Formative assessment extends beyond *tools*, important as these might be. It demands that teachers make decisions about the nature of feedback that they give to students and also its timing. It requires that they have an understanding of the misconceptions that students might have in particular areas of mathematics and the teaching and learning strategies that could help to address these misconceptions. It calls for them to be familiar with learning trajectories in various topics which they can use to design appropriate learning tasks and also to assess students’ learning. But above all, it necessitates that teachers are empowered to develop a learning environment in mathematics where there is a focus on co-construction of knowledge by teacher and students, and where students are given autonomy in the assessment as well as in the learning process.

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